

“Agroforestry in Austria” network

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Under climate change, arable farming in East Austria has been affected by increasing extreme weather conditions such as drought and farmers are seeking new ways for more resilient farming methods to respond to the changing climatic conditions. As a result, agroforestry as a traditional land management form has raised interest among Austrian farmers. In this context, EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” created a multi-actor agroforestry network for exchange of agroforestry information and experiences between science and practice in Austria.

Photo 1. A field visit of the agroforestry network participants at an agroforestry farm in Austria (FiBL, T. Markut).

Creation of an Austrian agroforestry network as one aim for the project

In Austria, no agroforestry network for networking, knowledge exchange and communication existed before the EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” in which formation of agroforestry network was one central aim. The project was run from October 2019 to September 2022 with a budget of 228642.85 euros. The aims of the “Agroforestry in Austria” project were 1) formation of a network on agroforestry, 2) know-how transfer on agroforestry to Austria with special consideration of the findings of the international EIP-Agri Focus Group Agroforestry,

3) identification of suitable agroforestry systems for different locations and farm orientations in eastern Austria, 4) concrete planning and implementation of agroforestry systems on six project farms (agroforestry model farms), 5) documentation of implementation steps, practical successes and challenges, as well as decision-making processes, 6) creation of information materials tailored to the target group of stakeholders interested in agroforestry, and 7) dissemination of the project results and agroforestry knowledge among farmers, (organic) farming advisors and other actors in the agricultural sector.

The diverse partner composition of the “Agroforestry in Austria” project created core basis for the multi-actor agroforestry network and its activities. Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL coordinated the project with partners being six Austrian agricultural holdings interested in agroforestry (model farms), Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), Consulting & Design Burkhard Kayser, Grottenhof/Hardt Technical College and Hatzendorf Plant Cultivation Experimental Station, Institute of Organic Agriculture and Department of Viticulture and Fruit Growing & Institute of Organic Farming at University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), organic farming association Bio-Austria in Lower Austria, and Lower Austria Chamber of Agriculture.

Other partners for agroforestry promotion, dissemination and education were agroforestry association ARGE Agroforst and Rural Training Institute Ländliches Fortbildungsinstitut Österreich.

Photo 2. A 11-year-old agroforestry system with hybrid poplar for wood chip production and arable crops in the state of Styria in Austria (FiBL, T. Markut).

Agroforestry network composition and activities

EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” created a multi-actor “Agroforestry in Austria” network. The agroforestry network consists of six participating agroforestry model farms with an interest in developing agroforestry systems on their arable land. Besides the agroforestry model farms, the EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” partners, stakeholders with previously established agroforestry systems, and other stakeholders interested in agroforestry are involved in the network.

Different types of knowledge are shared in the agroforestry network including farming practices, scientific and advisory expertise on agroforestry systems, administrative and policy related knowledge, and practical know-how on agroforestry.

The agroforestry network organizes agroforestry field trips, facilitates learning possibilities from good practice examples, provides knowledge and information on agroforestry systems, facilitates interaction and collaboration among stakeholders, and creates visibility for agroforestry in Austria. The network has made field trips for learning about good practices also in the neighbouring countries, such as in Switzerland. The activities of the agroforestry network are mainly project-financed.

Communication activities are key in the agroforestry network. During the “Agroforestry in Austria” project, the coordinator of EIP-Agri Operational Group Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL maintained the network. The agroforestry model farms were a central part of agroforestry related information production and were sites for fields visits.

Besides face-to-face events, dissemination and information materials addressing specific stakeholder groups in the agroforestry network and beyond were created. The project website [Agroforst in Österreich](#) collects all project materials and additional agroforestry resources in one place for stakeholders. Freely accessible information brochure for Austrian farmers “[Agroforestry – from idea to implementation](#)” was published in German both in printed and electronic format. The brochure gives overview of the most important aspects to be considered in planning and implementing agroforestry systems on arable land in Austria.

An introduction booklet on agroforestry “[Agroforestry – implementation on the farm: what needs to be considered when giving advice?](#)” was published in the local language, German, targeting especially stakeholders working in advisory and consultancy. Two videos in German on practical planning and implementation of agroforestry at farm level “[Agroforestry – from the idea to implementation](#)” and “[Agroforestry - many advantages for the farm and the environment](#)” were produced targeting especially farmers.

Photo books showcasing agroforestry system planting and maintenance and diversity of agroforestry systems were created as suggested by farmers in the agroforestry network. Information panels on agroforestry were installed on the agroforestry model farms for informing the public about the practiced agroforestry systems.

Photo 3. Agroforestry with alternating rows of valuable timber and rows of fast-growing tree species in 8th growing year in the state of Upper Austria in Austria (FiBL, T. Markut).

Agroforestry network after the completion of the “Agroforestry in Austria” project

The Austrian agroforestry network started during the EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” has continued to inspire stakeholders even after its completion. After the completion of the “Agroforestry in Austria” project, the agroforestry network has been maintained through the website of the project and follow-up projects under the umbrella of Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL. The follow-up projects have included Agroforestry Education Initiative in 2023-2024 which aimed at disseminating agroforestry implementation relevant information to farms based on the experiences and learnings in “Agroforestry in Austria” project, and at producing additional information materials on agroforestry such as brochures, factsheet and videos.

Another project in 2023-2025 aimed at analysing contribution of agroforestry systems on biodiversity and communicating of the findings also the public through an agroforestry map in Austria in which different agroforestry systems are showcased. In 2023-2025 StartClim project aimed at demonstrating contribution of agroforestry systems to alleviating climate change and advancing biodiversity by assessing carbon dioxide sequestration potential of agroforestry systems and by analysing their benefits to biodiversity and communicating the results to the public. The follow-up projects have supported the maintenance of multi-actor agroforestry network for advancing visibility of agroforestry among farmers, policymakers and other stakeholders.

About FOREST4EU project

The article has been produced in FOREST4EU project as a part of capacity building materials directed to stakeholders across Europe. Whereas innovations developed in the operational groups are typically available locally, FOREST4EU project aims at transferring knowledge and best practices on forestry and agroforestry to stakeholders and operational groups across Europe.

Photo 4. A 10-year-old agroforestry system with black walnut and mulberry in the state of Lower Austria in Austria (FiBL, T. Markut).

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Further information

[Visit the project page: “Agroforestry in Austria” network](#)

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